

Casma-Sechín Culture Religion

Secondary source

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Prehistoric South American Religions, Pre-Inka Religions, Peru, Andes, Religious Group, Animist, Military Cults, Language, Unknown, South American Religions

The Sechín archaeological complex was discovered by Julio C. Tello in 1937 during his visits to the Casma valley (Ancash). The record of the first settlers of the valley was made by Kosok, Malpass, Pozorski, Pozorski, Fung, among others and the first monumental buildings were studied by Peter Fuchs at the sites of Cerro Sechín and Sechín Bajo, which characterize the valley between 3400 to 1800 BC. The oldest ceremonial structure recorded is the First Building of the Sechín Bajo site, which consists of a platform with successive sunken circular plazas, built with stones, mud and hand-made rectangular adobes. This first building was in operation between 3500 to 3000 BC. and it is the oldest evidence found so far of monumental architecture in the Andean area.

Date Range: 3400 BCE - 1800 BCE

Region: Casma-Sechín region

Region tags: Peru, South America

Territory covered by the lower-middle Casma-Sechín Valley during the Late Archaic to the Early Formative Periods (3400 BC-1800 BC)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Tello, Julio César. 1956. *Arqueología del Valle de Casma*. Culturas: Chavín, Santa o Huaylas Yunga y Sub-Chimú. Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos.
- Source 2: Williams, Carlos. 1985. «A Scheme for the Early Monumental Architecture of the Central Coast of Peru». Pp. 227-40 en *Early Ceremonial Architecture in the Andes*, editado por C. B. Donnan. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection.
- Source 3: Pozorski, Shelia, y Thomas Pozorski. 1987. *Early Settlement and Subsistence in the Casma Valley, Peru*. Iowa City: University of Iowa Press.
- Source 1: Collier, Donald. 1960. «Archaeological Investigations in the Casma Valley, Peru». *Akten Des 34. Internationalen Amerikanistenkongresses* 411-17.
- Source 2: Tabío, Ernesto. 1977. *Prehistoria de la costa del Perú*. La Habana: Academia de Ciencias de Cuba.
- Source 3: Canziani, J. 2012. *Ciudad y territorio en los Andes*. Contribuciones a la historia del urbanismo prehisánico, 2da edición. PUCP. Lima, Perú

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://books.openedition.org/ifea/7357>
- Source 1 Description: GIER SZ, Miłosz (dir.) ; GHEZZI, Iván (dir.). *Arqueología de la Costa de Ancash*. Nueva edición [en línea]. Varsovia ; Lima: Institut français d'études andines, 2011 (generado el 04 abril 2024). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.ifea.7357>.
- Source 2 URL: <https://revistas.pucp.edu.pe/index.php/boletindeferqueologia/article/view/1649>
- Source 2 Description: Fuchs, P., Patzschke, R., Schmitz, C., Yenque, G., & Briceño, J. (2006). Investigaciones arqueológicas en el sitio de Sechín Bajo, Casma. *Boletín De Arqueología PUCP*, (10), 111-135. <https://doi.org/10.18800/boletindeferqueologiapucp.200601.006>
- Source 3 URL: https://www.iai.spk-berlin.de/fileadmin/dokumentenbibliothek/Indiana/Indiana_6/IND_06_Samaniego.pdf
- Source 3 Description: SAMANIEGO, Lorenzo 1980 "Informe sobre los hallazgos en Sechín. Monumentos arqueológicos de la costa norte del Perú," en *Indiana*, 6: 307- 348.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://revistas.pucp.edu.pe/index.php/boletindeferqueologia/article/view/977/944>
- Source 1 Description: Bischof, Henning. 2009. «Los periodos Arcaico Tardío, Arcaico Final y Formativo Temprano en el valle de Casma: evidencias e hipótesis». *Boletín de Arqueología PUCP* (13):9-54.
- Source 2 URL: <https://repositorio.cultura.gob.pe/handle/CULTURA/797>
- Source 2 Description: Fung, Rosa, y Carlos Williams. 1977. «Exploraciones y excavaciones en el valle de Sechín, Casma». *Revista del Museo Nacional XLIII*:111-55.
- Source 3 URL: <http://revistas.pucp.edu.pe/index.php/boletindeferqueologia/article/view/717/694>
- Source 3 Description: Pozorski, Shelia, y Thomas Pozorski. 1998. LA DINAMICA DEL VALLE DE CASMA DURANTE EL PERIODO INICIAL. *BOLETIN DE ARQUEOLOGIA PUCP*, 2, 83-100.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of significant interaction between Sechín and other religious cultures until near the end of the Initial period, around 1400 BC (see Pozorski and Pozorski, 2011 in Giersz and Ghezzi ed. in *Arqueología de la Costa de Ancash*).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As in most political entities, there were restricted and public religious activities led by a priest/specialist-religious. It is unknown if there was any payment during that period, but some compensation is estimated due to the social relevance that these activities had.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The political organization during that period was complex, since due to the magnitude of the buildings, the leaders mobilized an enormous workforce specialized in construction, production (conical adobes), adobe friezes, lithic art, which was compensated through the administration of irrigated agriculture, marine resources and religious events

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: As the authors of the references mention, there is a political benefit in favor of the community through the administration of basic resources: water, marine, contact with other settlements within the same political sphere, etc.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 18000

Notes: It is estimated that approximately 18,000 people inhabited the Upper Sechin Complex during its peak, and this complex ruled sites near Sechin Complex with an additional total population of approximately 5,000 people. However, the total number of adherents to the religious group cannot be specified (see Pozorski and Pozorski, 2011)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 75000

Notes: The Sechin Complex was a large proto-urban settlement several miles in diameter, centred on the large mound of Sechin Alto (300m x 250m). The Complex included the sites of

Sechin Bajo, Taukachi-Konkan, and Cerro Sechin. see Pozorski and Pozorski, 2011

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 35

Notes: Sechin Alto see Pozorski and Pozorski, 2011

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At least 4 tombs recorded but doesn't know the source

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No cemeteries have been recorded/found yet

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated

using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JaleUi6H_jc

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: some friezes had color

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many of these sites are oriented towards sacred hills or between hills and have the first events that impacted the political entity of Sechín Alto, such as the El Niño Phenomenon in 1400 BC

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During the early periods there were various deities and representations that influenced the formation of later gods.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many anthropomorphic figures, mostly decapitators and warriors with explicit parts of internal organs of the human body and animals such stylized figures of felines with some snakes appendix, may have been considered supernatural beings

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: It can be seen in lithic iconography and adobe freizes such as anthropomorphic and zoomorphic representations

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From the lithic art it could be warriors from neighboring groups

Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

Elites:

– Field doesn't know

Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has not yet been determined

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: San Pedro cactus (hallucinogen)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Although the Pozorskis and Bishoff dispute the term "state" for Sechín due to the proportion between labor and territory, the dynamic in the Casma valley is different. For the Early Formative there seem to be several competing centers (Sechín-Moxeque and Las Aldas towards the end of the period and even others), like small-city-states without being one, and at some point Sechin is supposedly the largest (complex) because it has more annexed sites.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is suggested that large-scale irrigated agriculture was the impetus for the increase in population and massive construction. However, it is not known if there was direct control by the religious group over these resources.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Through lithic art, warriors can be differentiated; however, It cannot be assumed some enforce institutionalized punishment

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Through lithic art, warriors can be differentiated; however, there are no records of fortresses or defensive buildings.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Chankillo Archaeoastronomical Complex (2300 BC) its a solar observatory in Coastal Peru, functioned as a calendrical instrument, using the sun to define dates throughout the year. Known as the Fortified Temple, two building complexes called Observatory and Administrative Centre, has a line of 13 towers allows the observation both of the solar rising and setting points throughout the whole year. See Ghezzi, I. (2010). "Chankillo, Peru" Ruggles y Cotte (eds.), *Heritage sites of astronomy and archaeoastronomy in the context of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention: A thematic study*, pp. 59-61. Ghezzi, I. (2008). "Chankillo, a Solar Observatory in Coastal Peru." En *Foundations of New World Cultural Astronomy*, Aveni (ed.): 181-198. Ghezzi, I. (2008). "Las Trece Torres de Chankillo: arqueoastronomía y organización social en el primer observatorio solar de América." En *Boletín de Arqueología PUCP*, 10: 215-236. UNESCO, the list: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1624>

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

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